

Supplementary File S1. Full Search Strategies

Database	Search string
PubMed (MEDLINE via PubMed)	(("Caregivers"[Mesh] OR caregiver*[Title/Abstract] OR "family caregiver*" [Title/Abstract] OR "informal caregiver*" [Title/Abstract]) AND ("Neoplasms"[Mesh] OR cancer[Title/Abstract] OR neoplasm*[Title/Abstract] OR oncolog*[Title/Abstract] OR tumor*[Title/Abstract] OR tumour*[Title/Abstract]) AND ("caregiver burden"[Title/Abstract] OR burden[Title/Abstract]) AND (scale*[Title/Abstract] OR instrument*[Title/Abstract] OR questionnaire*[Title/Abstract] OR assessment[Title/Abstract]))
	Search date: February 21, 2026. Filters applied: English, Italian, Humans. Study types were screened manually to retain primary quantitative studies.
Scopus (Elsevier)	TITLE-ABS-KEY ((caregiver* OR "family caregiver*" OR "informal caregiver*") AND (cancer OR neoplasm* OR oncolog* OR tumor* OR tumour*)) AND ("caregiver burden" OR burden) AND (scale* OR instrument* OR questionnaire* OR assessment)
	Search date: February 21, 2026. Filters applied: English, Italian, Humans. Study types were screened manually to retain primary quantitative studies.
Web of Science Core Collection (Clarivate)	TS=((caregiver* OR "family caregiver*" OR "informal caregiver*") AND (cancer OR neoplasm* OR oncolog* OR tumor* OR tumour*)) AND ("caregiver burden" OR burden) AND (scale* OR instrument* OR questionnaire* OR assessment)
	Search date: February 21, 2026. Filters applied: English, Italian, Humans. Study types were screened manually to retain primary quantitative studies.
CINAHL Complete (EBSCOhost)	((MH "Caregivers+") OR caregiver* OR "family caregiver*" OR "informal caregiver*") AND ((MH "Neoplasms+") OR cancer OR neoplasm* OR oncolog* OR tumor* OR tumour*) AND ("caregiver burden" OR burden) AND (scale* OR instrument* OR questionnaire* OR assessment)
	Search date: February 21, 2026. Filters applied: English, Italian, Humans. Study types were screened manually to retain primary quantitative studies.
PsycINFO (EBSCOhost)	(caregiver* OR "family caregiver*" OR "informal caregiver*") AND (cancer OR neoplasm* OR oncolog* OR tumor* OR tumour*) AND ("caregiver burden" OR burden) AND (scale* OR instrument* OR questionnaire* OR assessment)
	Search date: February 21, 2026. Filters applied: English, Italian, Humans. Study types were screened manually to retain primary quantitative studies.